

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINT AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF CADMIUM COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour and form	m.p. (°C)	Conductance (mhos, cm ²)	% Cadmium		% Halogen or Thiocyanate	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
CdCl ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	White Crystalline	>260	8	27.98	28.28	17.72	17.86
CdBr ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	"	242	8.5	22.86	23.12	32.66	32.87
CdI ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	"	235	11.4	19.14	19.37	43.62	43.78
Cd(NO ₃) ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	"	180	13.2	24.68	24.96	—	—
Cd(NCS) ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	"	195	15	25.22	25.40	25.84	26.22
[Cd(3 : 5-lut) ₄](ClO ₄) ₂	"	220	250	14.85	15.20	—	—
CdCl ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	"	210	8.5	28.05	28.28	17.62	17.86
CdBr ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	"	202	11	22.88	23.12	32.54	32.87
CdI ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	"	195	11.5	19.15	19.37	43.28	43.78
Cd(NO ₃) ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	"	182	10.2	24.71	24.96	—	—
Cd(NCS) ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	"	198	10.8	25.21	25.40	25.95	26.22

3 : 5-lut=3,5-dimethyl pyridine, 3-Etpty=3-ethylpyridine.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRA OF NITRATO, THIOCYANATO AND PERCHLORATE COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹)

Compound	ν ₂ (B ₂) out of plane rocking	Assignment ν ₁		ν ₂ (A ₁) (N-O)	ν ₃ (ClO ₄)	NO ₂ ν ₂ (A ₁) Sym.	Stretch ν ₄ (B ₁) Asym.	ν(C≡N)
		ν(C-S)	(ClO ₄)					
Cd(NO ₃) ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	785 m	—	—	1055 s	—	1235 s	1400 s	—
Cd(NO ₃) ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	790 m	—	—	1060 s	—	1280 s	1400 s	—
Cd(NCS) ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	—	820 s	—	—	—	—	—	2080 vs
Cd(NCS) ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	—	815 s	—	—	—	—	—	2065 vs
[Cd(3 : 5-lut) ₄](ClO ₄) ₂	—	—	935 m	—	1115 br (1060-1140)	—	—	—

the present investigation are four coordinated, presumably having a tetrahedral environment around the metal ion.

It is concluded that 3-ethyl pyridine and 3 : 5-dimethyl pyridine are considered to have good donor ability. In case the substituents would have reduced these ligands to poor donors due to steric factors, six-coordinated complexes could have been synthesised easily (instead of the four coordinated obtained now), since in case of a poor donor, more number of ligand molecules will be required to satisfy the acceptor capacity of the metal ion.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Mercury Using 5, 6-Dibromo, 2, 3, 4-Trihydroxy Acetophenone

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THE presence of traces of mercury in the environment has caused concern because of its cumulative toxic effects¹. The different techniques used for the determination of small amounts of mercury have been recently reviewed by Chilov². Although the

sensitivity of atomic absorption with the flameless and cold vapour modification and neutron activation in the determination of trace amounts of mercury is satisfactory, these techniques are not yet commonly used in most of the analytical laboratories and these techniques have their own limitations.

In general, the photometric methods are ideal for microanalysis when a suitable and specific colorimetric reagent is available for a particular determination.

Dithiazone is the most widely used reagent for the colorimetric determination of mercury, ($\epsilon = 5 \times 10^4$) up to 0.1 ppm and under ideal conditions, it can be used to detect as low as 0.01 ppm of mercury. Several dyes have been used to extract mercury into another phase as mercury(II) complex or as an ion association complex. Yet, no other photometric reagent has shown itself to be superior to dithiazone. It should be noted here that there are many drawbacks of dithiazone such as the instability of the reagent and mercury-reagent complex⁸. Dithiazone is not a specific photometric reagent⁸, the reagent shows a strong absorption in the region where the mercury-reagent complex has absorption maxima.

The net molar absorptivity of mercury-DBTHAP complex is about one-seventh of mercury-dithiazone complex. However, it is comparable with most of the mercury-dye complexes reported in literature. The proposed indicator is more specific than the others reported in the literature for mercury.

Experimental

Investigations of the determination of mercury with DBTHAP confirms that Beer's law is obeyed up to a concentration of 20 ppm of mercury and that the absorption of mercury-DBTHAP complex at 450 nm was constant over pH range 5.5 to 6.25. Out of the various buffers tried, Sodium Hydroxide-Potassium Hydrogen Phthalate buffer was observed to give best results.

Method

Apparatus :

Spectrophotometer,—A Beckmann DU-2, U.V.-Visible, spectrophotometer equipped with 1 cm matched quartz cells was used for all the absorption measurements.

The pH measurements were carried out on Elico IL-12 pH meter equipped with glass and calomel electrodes.

Reagents :

All the reagents should be of Analytical reagent grade.

Mercury chloride solution ($5 \times 10^{-4} M$) and Potassium Phthalate-Sodium Hydroxide buffer (pH 5.8) were prepared in distilled water. The reagent solution ($3 \times 10^{-4} M$) was prepared in absolute ethyl alcohol.

Preparation of Calibration Graph :

Take 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 ml of standard mercury solution into six different 25 ml standard flasks. Add 2 ml of $3 \times 10^{-4} M$ reagent (DETHAP) solution into each flask. Adjust the pH to 5.8 using buffer solution and dilute to 25 ml with double distilled water. Absorbance is measured for each solution against the corresponding reagent blank (It was observed that Beer's law holds good up to 20 ppm of mercury).

Procedure

Take an aliquot containing up to 20 ppm of mercury solution in 25 ml standard flask. Add to it 2 ml of $3 \times 10^{-4} M$ of reagent (alcoholic) solution. Adjust the pH 5.8 using buffer solution and dilute to the mark with double distilled water.

Record the absorbance at 450 nm against the corresponding reagent blank. Deduce the amount of mercury in the sample from the calibration graph.

Results and Discussion

It was observed that the molar absorptivity of the Hg-DPTHAP complex is 8.25×10^8 and its photometric sensitivity is $0.025 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. The composition of the complex as determined by the Job's method and the Mole ratio method was found to be 1 : 1. Ions like Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), Sr(II), Ca(II), Ba(II), Mg(II), Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- and CH_3COO^- can be tolerated even when present in ten fold excess. However, ions like V(V), Ti(IV), I^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and BrO_3^- interfere and should be absent.

Unlike most reagents used for the photometric determination of mercury, DBTHAP does not absorb significantly at the absorbance maximum (450 nm) of its mercury complex. The absorbance of mercury-DBTHAP system under the experimental conditions, pH 5.8, is reasonably constant for about half an hour; this time interval is more than sufficient for most analytical work.

The net molar absorptivity of mercury-DBTHAP complex is about one-seventh that of mercury-dithiazone complex. However, it is comparable with most of the mercury-dye complexes reported in literature. It should be noted that there is no interference of common metals associated with mercury using DBTHAP. The determination is also rapid as it does

not involve any lengthy procedure of solvent extraction. The new reagent is more suitable for comparatively higher concentration of mercury.

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Heats of Formation and Lattice Energies of Morpholine and Dioxan Complexes of Cobalt, Nickel, Copper and Zinc Fluoborates

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HEATS of formation and lattice energies of picoline complexes of copper fluoborate have been already reported¹. In this note heats of formation and lattice energies of morpholine and dioxan complexes of Co, Ni, Cu and Zn fluoborates have been determined. The isolation and characterisation of these complexes have been already reported²⁻³.

Fluoborate salts have been selected because the BF_4^- itself has got a tendency to take part in coordination and i.r. spectra study shows that BF_4^- serves as a bridge in the case of morpholine complex of cobalt².

In each case three readings were taken and the mean has been reported. Heats of formation (Q) determined by applying⁴ Hess's law of heat summation are given in the Table 1.

Calculation of Lattice Energy—Of the available equations⁵ for the calculation of lattice energy that of Kapustiniskii⁵ was found simple. But in these cases the values of ν (distance between the centre of the central cation and that of the co-ordinating atom) were not found in the literature and so the values of r_c (radii of the complex cations) and E_s (co-ordination energy) could not be calculated. Biltz and Grim⁶ have shown that the lattice energy of ammoniates is the sum of the two energies, namely the lattice energy of the ammonia free salts and the heat of formation of the ammoniates. In this present investigation, help has been taken from Biltz and Grim's work. Lattice energies of anhydrous fluoborates (U_1) were determined by two equations of Kapustiniskii⁵ and Yatsimirskii⁷. The values of lattice energies (U_2) are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	U_1 , K cal/mole	Q K cal/mole	U_2 , K cal/mole
$\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Morpho	508.3	23.16	531.46
$\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Morpho	508.3	11.10	519.40
$\text{Cu}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Morpho	504.66	32.90	537.46
$\text{Cu}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Morpho	504.66	16.03	520.69
$\text{Zn}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Morpho	493.0	22.72	515.72
$\text{Zn}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Morpho	493.0	9.62	502.62
$\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Dioxan	508.3	34.83	543.13
$\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Dioxan	508.3	18.33	526.63
$\text{Ni}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Dioxan	510.5	38.39	548.89
$\text{Ni}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Dioxan	510.5	23.37	533.87
$\text{Cu}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Dioxan	504.66	26.00	530.66
$\text{Cu}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Dioxan	504.66	14.00	518.66
$\text{Zn}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Dioxan	493.0	26.30	519.30
$\text{Zn}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Dioxan	493.0	12.52	505.52

It is found in all the cases that as the number of ligand molecules decreases in a particular metal complex, the lattice energy value also decreases. It seems that as the number of ligands increases the crystal becomes more densely packed and hence the lattice energy value increases.

Similarly the lattice energy value decreases when the number of ligand molecules decreases as the crystal now becomes less densely packed.

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TLC Separation of Some Inorganic Ions on Silica Gel-Ceric Molybdate Impregnated Layers

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RECENTLY Malik and coworkers¹, have reported the ion-exchange behaviour of ceric molybdate. In the present study, we have utilised the ion-exchange property of ceric molybdate for the TLC separation of some closely related inorganic ions.